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**Lenvatinib halts aortic aneurysm growth
by restoring smooth muscle cell contractility**

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Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Abstract

Rationale: To evaluate the repurposing of lenvatinib, a multi tyrosine kinase inhibitor, in limiting experimental abdominal aortic aneurysm (AAA) growth.

Objective: AAA is a disease with high morbidity and mortality, especially in case of rupture. No pharmacologic treatment is currently available. Novel therapeutic strategies are targeting vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMC) and angiogenesis. Repurposing of clinically available drugs has proven its benefit to extend treatment strategies and may be suited to halt aortic dilatation.

Findings: Porcine pancreatic elastase (PPE) was used to induce murine AAAs. Systemic and local lenvatinib forms of treatment were evaluated, and RNA profiling identified myosin heavy chain 11 (*Myh11*) as the most deregulated transcript. Daily oral treatment significantly reduced aneurysm formation in two independent mouse models. In addition, a novel large animal aneurysm model in hypercholesterolemic low-density lipoprotein receptor knockout (*LDLR*^{-/-}) Yucatan minipigs was applied to endovascularly deliver lenvatinib *via* drug-eluting balloons (DEB). Here, a single local endovascular delivery blocked AAA progression successfully compared to a DEB-delivered control treatment when reaching 28 days post aneurysm induction. Reduced VSMC proliferation and a restored contractile phenotype were observed in animal tissues (murine and porcine), as well as AAA patient-derived cells. Apart from increasing MYH11 levels, lenvatinib reduced downstream ERK signaling.

Conclusion: Lenvatinib is a promising new therapy to limit aortic aneurysm expansion upon local endovascular delivery. The tyrosine kinase inhibitor was able to positively affect pathways of key relevance to human AAA disease. The novel endovascular local delivery using DEBs offers new treatment strategies for additional therapies capable of slowing down aneurysm expansion.

Introduction

AAA is a diameter enlargement of the infrarenal aorta by 1.5-fold or bigger. The susceptible population has an age dependent prevalence of 3-11%.⁽¹⁾ Due to the risk of rupture, aneurysm disease is among the leading causes of death in Western countries. Risk factors include arterial hypertension, hyperlipidemia, male sex, family history, and smoking. International guidelines recommend treatment upon a threshold diameter of 5.5cm and modern treatment favors endovascular over open repair, despite similar long-term results.⁽²⁾

The pathogenesis of AAA is not yet fully understood, and the mechanisms triggering disease development and progression remain unclear. In particular, the initial event and site-specific occurrence of aneurysm formation is largely elusive, prompting recent interest into better experimental models and research in general.⁽¹⁾ Some crucial mechanisms have been well characterized, including local wall stress alteration, enzymatic and mechanical intraluminal thrombus formation, proteolytic imbalance, and a humoral immune answer as a possible repair or healing mechanism.⁽³⁾ Moreover, phenotypic changes in VSMCs and the hypoxic micro-milieu that involves angiogenesis in the aortic media have gained some attention and experimental therapies aimed at addressing them.⁽⁴⁾

Lately, we were able to demonstrate a positive effect on halting AAA growth by RNA interference targeting the long non-coding RNA H19, which represses HIF1 α signaling and its apoptotic effect on VSMCs during aneurysm progression.⁽⁵⁾ Others have demonstrated that influencing VSMC signaling and plasticity alters aneurysm growth in experimental mouse models.⁽⁶⁾ However, small animal models remain limited in their ability to mimic human disease, and thus making it impossible to test local and site-specific delivery of therapeutics directly into the aortic wall.⁽⁷⁾

To date, several treatment strategies using established drugs with other indications were successfully tested in rodent AAA models (e.g., doxycycline or sartans). Some have even entered small scale clinical trials, however, failed to limit aneurysm growth and rupture risk in patients.(8) Still, drug repurposing has emerged as a new way to limit cost and time for compound development, by expanding the spectrum of approved medications to new or additional applications.(9) The multi tyrosine kinase inhibitor (TKI) lenvatinib is used to block angiogenesis in cancer therapy (*i.e.*, thyroid cancer).(10) Its inhibition of vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2 (VEGFR2) makes it a suitable repurposed candidate to potentially limit AAA progression. Thus, we decided to investigate the potential of systemic and endovascular local lenvatinib delivery to halt aneurysm growth in experimental murine models, primary human AAA patient-derived cells, and a novel preclinical Yucatan *LDLR*^{-/-} minipig AAA model.

Results

Lenvatinib halts aneurysm growth in murine AAA and induces MYH11 expression

Mice with PPE-induced AAAs were treated daily with lenvatinib (bodyweight-adjusted) *via* oral gavage as previously established by others.(11) Treatment started 7 days after aneurysm induction when a small AAA had already developed upon PPE instillation.(7) Lenvatinib completely halted aneurysm growth over the following 3 weeks until sacrifice (fold increase of dilation in Figure 1A, absolute values in Suppl. Figure 1A, detailed weekly measurements in Suppl. Table 1). Aortic tissue RNA profiling using the mouse transcriptome array (*MTA_1.0*) analyzing untreated animals (normal aorta), PPE-induced AAAs (PPE), and lenvatinib treated animals (PPE + Lenva systemic) revealed *Myh11* as the most significantly deregulated transcript (Figure 1B, Figure 2E, Suppl. Figure 4A,B) when comparing all subgroups (downregulated in PPE vs. normal aorta; upregulated in PPE + Lenva systemic vs. PPE).

MYH11 is an established marker for the contractile phenotype of VSMCs, and known to be decreased in AAA compared to non-aneurysmal controls.(12) Immunohistochemical analysis revealed substantially higher levels of MYH11 present in the media of normal aortas, as well as in lenvatinib treated PPE-AAA, however, was completely absent in regular PPE-induced AAAs (Figures 1C-E, Suppl. Figure 2, quantification in Figure 2A). CD31-positive cells indicated angiogenic activity in the media and endothelium of PPE-AAAs, whereas solely the endothelium was marked in control and lenvatinib-treated animals (Figures 1C-E, Suppl. Figure 1B). Thus, gene expression and immunohistochemistry, along with basic morphologic analysis using HE suggested a phenotypic aortic wall restoration upon lenvatinib treatment

with reduced angiogenesis, re-established MYH11 levels, and signs of amplified fibrosis. Bodyweight and basic blood laboratory analysis were unchanged between treatment and control groups (Suppl. Table 1). All established lenvatinib target receptors, especially *Vegfr2*, were deregulated in PPE-induced AAAs (Suppl. Figure 1C).(13)

Similarly, lenvatinib (delivered *via* daily oral gavage) reduced aortic diameter and volume in a confirmatory study using a second murine model of AAA disease, angiotension II (AngII) infusion in *ApoE*^{-/-} mice (Suppl. Figure 3). In line with our study in PPE-induced AAA, treatment in this model was once more started when aortic dilatation already occurred at day 4 upon induction (detailed weekly measurements in Suppl. Table 1).

In addition, did we test the potential benefit of local delivery of lenvatinib to the aorta, again 7 days after experimental aneurysm induction was performed in the PPE model (Figure 2B, C). Re-intervention and local perfusion of the established small AAA resulted in a significant diameter reduction compared to sham-intervened mice with AAA after 28 days (fold increase of diameters in Figure 2B; absolute values in Suppl. Figure 1D; detailed weekly measurements are summarized in Suppl. Table 1). Both, systemic oral and local lenvatinib treatment had analogous effects on completely halting AAA progression. A similar phenotypic salvage, with a more contained aortic structure and enhanced MYH11 levels after local lenvatinib treatment, could also be observed (Figures 2A,D). These effects were not detectable after local reperfusion with PBS, which attended as a surgical (sham) control experiment (Suppl. Figures 1D, E, 4B).

Lenvatinib affects VSMC plasticity in AAA patient-derived cells

To enhance translation of our finding, primary VSMC culture derived from three different AAA patients was obtained (age: 71 ± 3 y; diameter: 65 ± 5 mm; Figure 3, Suppl. Figures 5-7). Firstly, we discovered a dose dependent anti-proliferative and anti-migrative effect upon lenvatinib treatment *in vitro* on healthy human donor aortic smooth muscle cells (Suppl. Figure 6C). Then, cell mobility (wound scratch assay) and cell proliferation were also assessed in patient-derived AAA-VSMCs. Here, lenvatinib treatment significantly reduced both mobility and proliferation compared to cells treated with vehicle (DMSO) only (Figure 3). Apoptosis appeared at low rates in general and was not affected by lenvatinib treatment (Figure 3A). However, lenvatinib did significantly reduce apoptosis in VSMCs from healthy donors (Suppl. Figure 7A, right panel). RNA profiling identified a subset of genes typically involved in maintaining contractile VSMC function as significantly increased upon lenvatinib treatment in a time-dependent manner (Figure 3B; Suppl. Figures 5-7B; Suppl. Table 2). VEGFR2 (Kdr), a direct target of lenvatinib, was significantly downregulated in all *in vitro* experiments after 48h of treatment. AAA-patient derived cells displayed an accelerated reactivity – based on more substantial changes in gene expression – to lenvatinib in all assays (Figure 3; Suppl. Figures 5-7). Overall cell integrity of the patient-derived VSMCs was confirmed by cytoskeleton/contractile filament staining (Suppl. Figure 8).

Lenvatinib promotes a contractile VSMC phenotype and reduces ERK-signaling

In a collagen-based contractility assay, primary human AAA patient-derived VSMCs treated with lenvatinib displayed enhanced contractility in comparison to vehicle treated cells (Figure 4A, Suppl. Figure 9C) and significant up-regulation of contractile

cell markers (i.e. MYOCD and ACTA2) 24h after treatment initiation (Figure 4B; Suppl. Figure 9D).

In accordance with previously shown immunohistochemistry and gene expression data, Western Blot analysis also detected MYH11 markedly increased upon lenvatinib treatment (Figure 4C; Suppl. Figures 9A,B). When exploring possible downstream signaling pathways affected by lenvatinib, we discovered a decrease in the phospho-ERK1-2:total-ERK1-2 ratio in all cell experiments after 6 and 48h of lenvatinib exposure (Figure 4D; Suppl. Figure 10).

Lenvatinib coated balloon angioplasty blocks aneurysm progression in a preclinical Yucatan *LDLR*^{-/-} minipig model

To further test the potential of a local endovascular delivery of lenvatinib to halt aneurysm growth, we established a novel large animal model with inducible AAA in hypercholesterolemic *LDLR*^{-/-} Yucatan minipigs (Suppl. Figure 11A,B). Unlike *Ldlr*^{-/-} mice, which almost solely develop aortic lesions in their arch, *LDLR*-deficient minipigs present with severe atherosclerotic disease throughout the entire vascular system, including the infrarenal aorta (Figure 5A). Thus, this preclinical model very closely resembles the aged vascular phenotype of human AAA disease (Suppl. Figure 11D,12,14). (14) In addition to more closely mimicking the advanced human AAA phenotype, *LDLR*^{-/-} mini-pigs develop more enlarged AAAs compared to their wildtype normo-cholesterolemic companions (82±24% vs. 50±13% diameter increase; $p < 0.05$) 28 days after PPE induction. At baseline, the average diameter in *LDLR*^{-/-} (0.74±0.56cm) and *LDLR*^{+/+} (0.75±0.52cm) was almost identical, highlighting the pro-aneurysmal effect of the hypercholesterolemic mini-pigs.

The PPE instillation itself resulted in a significant increase of the aortic diameter (week1: 21±15%, $p = 0.0004$; week4: 56±21%, $p = 0.000002$; $n = 7$; Figure 5B;

Suppl. Table 1) compared to sham operation (PBS perfusion; at week 4: 10±9%; Suppl. Figure 11E). Compared to non-dilated *LDR^{-/-}* mini-pig aortas, PPE-induced aneurysms presented with significantly reduced MYH11 levels and CD31-positive neovessels in the aortic media of the dilated vessels (Figures 5C,D; Suppl. Figure 12).

Drug eluting balloon (DEB)-delivered lenvatinib treatment, 7 days after aneurysm induction, was capable of significantly reducing AAA diameters after 28 days in comparison to a control (vehicle only) DEB intervention in PPE-AAA animals (31% increase with lenvatinib-DEB vs. 68% increase with control-DEB; $p=0.006$; Figures 5A-B). The DEB-control intervention using vehicle (DMSO) only had no effect on aortic diameter progression compared to regular AAA development in PPE-induced AAAs in this porcine model (Suppl. Figure 11E).

Immunohistochemical analysis revealed high abundance of MYH11 co-localizing with α SMA in the aortic media (Figures 5C, D, 6B; Suppl. Figure 12). Consistently, Western Blot confirmed this result, with DEB-lenvatinib-treated pigs showing higher MYH11 protein levels compared to DEB-controls (Figure 5E). Accordingly, lenvatinib treatment significantly increased MYH11 protein levels in VSMCs isolated from healthy porcine aorta *in vitro* (Figure 5F, Suppl. Figure 13A). Bodyweight and blood parameters (white and red blood cell counts; measures of liver and kidney function) were unchanged between the treatment and control groups (Suppl. Table 3).

Human AAA tissue is deficient in VSMC contractile elements

Phenotypic switching in VSMCs in AAA disease has been demonstrated numerous times before.(6, 12, 15) We analyzed human AAA samples from an advanced disease state (6-7cm diameter) from patients undergoing open aortic repair. Here,

the morphology of AAA compared to non-dilated infrarenal aortic controls was completely altered in terms of elastic fibers degradation, disruption of the media and adventitia, angiogenesis in the aortic media, as well as inflammatory infiltrates (Suppl. Figure 14B). Gene expression analysis of characteristic SMC markers indicated a definite loss of contractile features in AAA compared to non-dilated control aortas (Suppl. Table 2). Double-immunofluorescent staining confirmed MYH11 being co-localized with α SMA in non-dilated aortas, but almost entirely absent in advanced AAA (Figure 6A; Suppl. Figures 14A,15).

Discussion

In this study, we successfully “re-purpose” the anti-cancer drug lenvatinib to halt experimental abdominal aortic aneurysm growth in two species and patient-derived primary human cells *via* reconstitution of VSMC contractility.

Our study provides evidence for the first non-cancer application of the TKI lenvatinib.(16, 17) Furthermore, for the first time we successfully treat animals with an already existing AAA, 7 days after aneurysm induction, and thus very closely mimic the translational need for treating an established aneurysm in patients (Figures 1A, 2B/E, 5A, Suppl. Figure 4A,B). Previous drug interaction studies start treatment in mice before – or at the time – of aneurysm induction (day 0), thus before disease onset, which might mainly counteract inflammatory processes seen in the early phases of all animal AAA models.(7, 18, 19) Imatinib and erlotinib are two TKIs with different target receptors (c-abl and epidermal growth factor receptor, respectively) that have shown the capacity to attenuate experimental aneurysm growth in the murine AngII-induced aortic dissection model.(20, 21)

In cancer therapy, lenvatinib is employed mainly for its anti-angiogenic effect.(16) Neo-angiogenesis in the aortic media is observed in human AAA and in the murine PPE model, but remains absent in non-dilated aortas (Figures 1C-E, 3B, 5D).(22, 23) We observed limited CD31/CD34 positivity as a hallmark of reduced angiogenesis in all lenvatinib-treated animals, as well as reduced expression of VEGFR2 in human AAA patient-derived primary cells (Figures 1E, 2D, 3B, 4B). Similarly, we have previously demonstrated aneurysm abrogation in the murine PPE and AngII model by blocking the long non-coding RNA H19, which represses HIF1 α expression and subsequent angiogenesis.(5) Interference with the HIF1 α -VEGF-VEGFRs axis has been shown multiple times to hinder aneurysm growth in mouse models.(4, 23, 24) One of the major reasons to select lenvatinib for our study was

that lenvatinib – of all TKIs – has the highest affinity for VEGFR2, which can be found abundantly in, both, human and experimental AAA.(22, 25, 26)

Despite angiogenesis, the fate of VSMCs in the aortic media may crucially determine the aneurysm expansion rate. HIF1 α is likely a key link between angiogenesis and VSMC phenotype polarization.(5, 27) Along with fragmentation of the elastic fibers and reorganization of the ECM architecture, the number of VSMCs declines substantially during AAA progression, while turnover increases with cells losing their contractile phenotype.(3, 28) These effects are strongly opposed by treatment with low dose lenvatinib, both, on a cellular level and in experimental AAA in mice and minipigs. While apoptosis seemed largely unaffected (an increase was only detectable in donor VSMCs) (Figure 3A, Suppl. Figures 5A, 7A), mobility and proliferation were markedly decreased, and many genes involved in maintaining the contractile phenotype (e.g., *TAGLN*, *CNN1*, *MYOCD*, *ITGA8*, *CALD1*) became strongly upregulated upon TKI treatment (Figure 3, Figures 5-7). However, *COL3A1*, which encodes the pro-alpha1 chains of type III collagen as main fibrillar component of the non-diseased aorta, typically expressed by synthetic SMCs, appeared repressed upon lenvatinib stimulation in all cell experiments, highlighting its effect in regulating phenotypic SMC-transitions towards the contractile state. MYH11, a prototypical contractile marker, gets substantially restored by lenvatinib (Figures 1B, 4C, 5E,F, 6B, Suppl. Figures 9A,B, 12, 13). Its regulatory role and contribution to an intact aortic wall, other than being a marker of the contractile apparatus, is largely unknown. However, it has been found repressed in aneurysmatic conditions in several studies.(29-31) Targeting VSMC dynamics and fate using RNA-based therapies or chemotherapeutics has largely been proven effective in different animal models of AAA.(32, 33) Moreover, ERK phosphorylation is a crucial mediator of AAA

expansion and VSMC differentiation. Various substances are capable of blocking ERK-1 phosphorylation and limiting aortic dilation.(34-36)

Interestingly, the magnitude of differential gene expression and the responsiveness to lenvatinib in cellular assays was enhanced in diseased (AAA patient-derived) cells compared to healthy donor cells. This suggests that the diseased state of VSMCs to be more susceptible to an external stimulus or treatment. Importantly, AAA patient-derived cells and healthy donor cells stem from the infrarenal aorta, excluding the embryologic origin to play any role in the outcome of our experiments. Interestingly, a higher extent of intracellular damage can be observed in AAA patient-derived cells.(12) This supports our recent attempts to initiate treatment not at the time of AAA induction in murine models, but rather when a dilation and progression of disease has already been established.(7)

Apart from systemic forms of application, we demonstrate the effectiveness of a local endovascular application of lenvatinib in mice and a novel atherosclerotic minipig model. The PPE procedure in pigs has successfully been performed before.(37) However, by using *LDLR*^{-/-} animals with advanced atherosclerosis, we are convinced to achieve a closer mimicry of advanced human AAA pathology.(14) While only male mice have been utilized to exclude sex-specific effects, a mixed group of female and castrated male pigs were used. Nevertheless, a very uniform aneurysm formation could be observed.(38)

From a translational perspective, the local treatment with a lenvatinib-coated balloon or stent(-graft) could be an amendment to difficult AAA morphologies with problematic proximal or distal sealing zones, as well as for otherwise inoperable patients.(39, 40) In ophthalmology, intra-vitreous bevacizumab, a monoclonal VEGF-blocker is already in common use for retinal artery aneurysm treatment.(41) We did not observe any side effects based on overall survival or organ function in our

lenvatinib treatment group. However, side effects are certainly possible and should be further evaluated in a more chronic, extended experimental setup with greater sample size, especially when considering the current debate on long term effects of Paclitaxel coated balloons.(42, 43)

Material and Methods

Methods unique to this study are summarized below. Additional materials and methods are presented in the **Online Data Supplement**.

Porcine pancreatic elastase and angiotensin II induction of murine aortic aneurysms

See **study approval section** for ethics declaration. The porcine pancreatic elastase (PPE; SigmaAldrich, Taufkirchen, Germany) model was described various times before.(13, 44) Briefly, ten-week-old male C57BL/6J wild type mice (Taconic Biosciences, Hudson, NY) on regular chow diet (R36; Lantmännen, Stockholm, Sweden) were kept under standard conditions (temperature 22°C, humidity 56%). Similarly, AngII-minipump implantation for AAA induction has been described various times before.(19) Briefly, ten-week-old ApoE^{-/-} male mice (Charles River, Sulzfeld, Germany) received an Angiotensin II (Bachem, Switzerland) loaded osmotic minipump (Model 2004, DURECT Corporation) implanted subcutaneously. Anesthesia, PPE-AAA induction, AngII-AAA Induction, murine B-mode ultrasound images, and protocols for euthanasia and tissue processing are discussed in the **Online Data Supplement**.

Oral lenvatinib treatment in mice

Anesthesia was induced using isoflurane. Each animal was fed an individual bodyweight dependent dose (5mg/kg) of 2.5mg/ml lenvatinib (E7080; Catalog No S1164, Selleckchem, Munich, Germany) solution dissolved in DMSO (SigmaAldrich, Taufkirchen, Germany) as used and reported before by others.(11) Oral gavage was performed by placing a pipet tip in glucose and then down the animal's throat. This procedure was repeated daily from day 7 (for PPE mice) and day 4 (for AngII mice)

until day 24 after AAA induction. The procedure was performed on 7 PPE and 6 AngII animals (no deaths, average procedure time 4 min per animal including anesthesia). Additionally, 5 AngII mice received oral gavage of PBS as a sham group.

Local lenvatinib treatment in mice

Anesthesia was induced with isoflurane, and analgesia was provided with buprenorphine (4mg/kg), before and after surgery, 7 days after the initial AAA induction with PPE. The retroperitoneum was re-exposed, and the established AAA was carefully dissected from the adherent soft tissue (illustrated in Figure 2A). Proximal to the initial aortic incision, a second intervention was performed using a 30G needle. Aneurysms were then perfused with a 2.5mg/ml lenvatinib solution in DMSO for 10 min *via* an inserted micro-catheter. Thereafter, the aorta was flushed with warm saline, and a single knot suture (10-0) was placed to seal the catheter entry site. After layered closure of the abdomen, the animal was allowed to recover under an infrared lamp. The procedure was performed on 6 animals; one animal died due to surgical blood loss during dissection (procedure time approx. 55 min including anesthesia).

Mouse transcriptomic array analysis

RNA profiling was performed using the Mouse Transcriptome Assay 1.0 (Affymetrix, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Differential expression analysis was achieved by utilizing the Transcriptome Analysis Console v4.0.1.36 (Affymetrix) in accordance with the manufacturer's default settings and SST-RMA summarization method. Three separate groups (non-dilated control aorta, PPE-AAA, PPE-AAA+Lenva treatment; same region of infrarenal aorta in all animals) of mouse aortic tissues were analyzed

for differential expression. The results were exported and further processed using RStudio v1.1.463/Rv3.5.3. Raw exported data and R Script files used for the analysis can be found in the Online Data Supplement. When applicable, for down-stream analyses, standard filtering was performed ($p < 0.05$, absolute fold change ≥ 2) and certain groups of genes were removed (unannotated genes, predicted genes, genes coding for immunoglobulin chains). Data from a separate own MTA 1.0. dataset of early PPE-model mice (PPE-AAA [n=6], Saline-Ctrl [n=5]; same region of infrarenal aorta harvested at day 7) was used to present baseline transcriptomic characteristics of the model at the timepoint of Lenva-treatment initiation, as shown in Figure 2E/Suppl. Figure 4A. KEGG-pathway gene overrepresentation analysis was performed using clusterProfiler v3.16.1 using directional sets of differentially regulated genes (Benjamini-Hochberg adjusted p-value < 0.05 , absolute fold change either ≤ -2 or ≥ 2). Plotting was performed using the ggplot2 v3.3.3 library.(45)

Abdominal aortic aneurysm induction in Yucatan minipigs

See **study approval section** for ethics declaration. Twelve 13-months-old female and castrated male *LDLR*^{-/-} Yucatan minipigs (77.8 ± 5.1 kg body weight) from Exemplar Genetics (Coralville, IA, United States) were used. Minipigs were housed in groups of 2-4 under conventional hygienic conditions and an acclimatization period of at least 9 days prior to surgery (temperature $19 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$; humidity 50–60%; 12h/12h light–dark cycle; environmental enrichment provided). Animals were fed with a pelleted high-fat diet (Altromin, Lage, Germany) twice a day and received water *ad libitum*. Prior to anesthesia, animals were starved for 12h with free access to water.

All experiments commonly consisted of three distinct procedures: baseline/day 0 (ultrasound and AAA induction with PPE), day 8 (ultrasound and endovascular coated balloon treatment *via* femoral access) and day 28 (ultrasound, euthanasia

and tissue collection). Detailed protocols for anesthesia and ultrasound measurements can be found in the Online Data Supplement. For the PPE induction, a retroperitoneal exposure of the aorta was achieved *via* a left lateral flank access. Preparation included anteflexion of the left kidney and complete dissection of the aorta from the left renal artery to the aortic trifurcation. 2-3 pairs of lumbar arteries were clipped and divided. 3000IU heparin were administered before clamping of the aorta over a distance of 3-4cm. A 9-11x20mm PTA balloon (Medtronic Admiral Xtreme, Medtronic, Santa Rosa, CA, USA) based on previous ultrasound measurements (diameter + 2mm) was inserted *via* puncture incision and inflated to 10atm for 1 min to pre-dilate the aorta, allowing better perfusion with the elastase. Afterwards, a blunt needle (5G) was inserted and perfusion with 10IU/ml PPE (SigmaAldrich, Taufkirchen, Germany) was started after a tourniquet secured the needle at the puncture site. The aorta was perfused to the maximum diameter before effusion of elastase through the vessel for 10 min using a pressure syringe was permitted. Afterwards, the aorta was flushed with heparinized saline (1000IU/L) and the incision closed with a 5-0 suture before re-opening the clamp. Layer-by-layer closure including 2x muscle, fat, and skin was performed, and the wound was coated with a spray-on-dressing (Aqueos, Sharcott, UK).

Endovascular drug eluting balloon (DEB) treatment in Yucatan minipigs

The animals were put in supine position. A 4 cm incision into the right groin was made and the common femoral artery was surgically exposed. 3000IU of heparin were administered. The vessel was then ligated distally before a 5F introducer sheath (TerumoAortic, Eschborn, Germany) was placed in retrograde direction. Using a Terumo guide wire (TerumoAortic, Eschborn, Germany) and a mobile C-arm, a 4F pig tail catheter (Aimecs, Pfarrkirchen, Germany) was advanced into the aorta.

An angiogram using 6ml of contrast agent (Imeron, Bracco, Germany) to identify aortic landmarks and the aneurysmatic lesion was performed. A 10-12x20mm PTA balloon (Medtronic Admiral Xtreme, Medtronic, Santa, Rosa, CA, USA) was then spray coated with a 50mM lenvatinib (E7080) solution. Using a special introducer sheath to protect the coated area, the balloon was advanced to the identified aneurysm site and inflated to 10atm for 3 min. Afterwards a control angiography excluded aortic occlusion or dissection. The common femoral artery was ligated proximally to the puncture site. Layer-by-layer closure was performed and coated with spray-on-dressing. Postoperative analgesia, blood sampling, and euthanasia protocols can be found in the Online Data Supplement.

Double immunofluorescence staining

2.5 µm sections of paraffin-embedded samples were mounted on pre-coated SuperFrost Plus slides (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Antigen retrieval and blocking of peroxidase activity was performed as described for IHC. Additional blocking with 5% horse serum was performed for 1h. Primary and secondary antibodies (Suppl. Table 4) were diluted in 5% horse serum. Both primary antibodies were incubated after another over/night each at 4°C, followed by both secondary antibodies for 1h each at the respective day. TrueBlack Lipofuscin Autofluorescence Quencher (Biotium, Fremont, CA, USA) was applied to reduce background fluorescence. Sections were counterstained with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and images were taken under a confocal microscope (TCS SP5 II, Leica, Wetzlar, Germany). For negative controls: only the secondary antibody was applied for 1h at room temperature; 5% horse serum without any primary antibody was applied over/night.

Primary cell culture of human aortic aneurysm VSMCs

Written and informed consent was obtained from all patients and approved by the local ethics committee.(46) Human AAA material was harvested during surgical repair and stored in complete DMEM/F12 Medium (Sigma Aldrich, Taufkirchen, Germany containing 5% FBS and 1% PS). The tissue was placed in a sterile petri dish and washed with PBS. Adventitia, neo-Intima and calcifications were removed, and the remaining media was cut into small pieces using a sterile scalpel. The pieces of tissue were placed in digestion medium (1.4mg/ml Collagenase A, Roche, Mannheim, Germany, in complete DMEM/F12 Medium) in a humidified incubator at 37°C and 5% CO₂ for 4-6 h. Cells were strained using a 100µm cell strainer to remove debris. After 2 washing steps (centrifuge 400g, 5 min; discard supernatant, re-suspended in 15ml complete DMEM/F12 Medium) cells were re-suspended in 7ml complete DMEM/F12 Medium and placed in a small cell culture flask in a humidified incubator at 37°C and 5% CO₂. Medium was changed every other day. After 1 week the medium was replaced by SMC Growth Medium (PeloBiotech, Planegg, Germany). Upon confluence, cells were stored in liquid nitrogen or processed immediately. In this study, primary cells (#1-3) from 3 different patients with AAAs (diameter 6.7 ± 0.4cm) were obtained. Cells were used between passages 3-7. Primary abdominal aortic SMCs from healthy donors (control SMCs) were purchased from Cell Applications (San Diego, CA, USA, 354-05a) and used between passages 5-7.

Dynamic live-cell imaging assays

All dynamic live-cell imaging experiments were performed following the instructions provided by Essen Bioscience (Ann Arbor, MI, USA) using the IncuCyte ZOOM system. *Dose finding experiment:* Cells were plated in 24-well plates

(Corning/Falcon, Tewksbury, MA, USA). Next day medium was changed to OptiMEM+10% FBS+1% PEST. Lenvatinib (E7080) was dissolved in 2.3ml DMSO (according to commercial protocol) to produce the 10mM stock solution. This stock was diluted into working concentrations: 10 μ M, 1 μ M and 0.1 μ M. 1 μ l DMSO was added to control wells. Confluence was assessed over 72h using the IncuCyte ZOOM System. *Proliferation and Apoptosis*: Cells were placed with 30% confluence in a 96-well plate and treated with 0.1 μ M lenvatinib in OptiMEM (Thermo Fisher, Planegg, Germany; lenvatinib-treatment) or 0.1% DMSO in OptiMEM (control-treatment) for 72h. The IncuCyte Caspase-3/7 Apoptosis Reagent (Essen Bioscience, Ann Arbor, MI, USA) was added at a final concentration of 5 μ M. The plate was monitored in the IncuCyte ZOOM System (Essen Bioscience, Ann Arbor, MI, USA) with phase/fluorescence and a 2h imaging pattern. Images were auto-collected and analyzed using the IncuCyte ZOOM software (Essen Bioscience, Ann Arbor, MI, USA). *Migration*: Cells were placed at 100% confluence in 96-well ImageLock plates (Essen Bioscience, Ann Arbor, MI, USA) and homogeneous 700-800 μ m wide wounds were created using the WoundMaker (Essen Bioscience, Ann Arbor, MI, USA). Cells were treated with 0.1 μ M lenvatinib in OptiMEM (Thermo Fisher, Planegg, Germany, lenvatinib-treatment) or 0.1% DMSO in OptiMEM (control-treatment) for 72h, and the plate was monitored in the IncuCyte ZOOM System (Essen Bioscience, Ann Arbor, MI, USA) with a 2h imaging pattern. Images were auto-collected and analyzed using the IncuCyte ZOOM software (Essen Bioscience, Ann Arbor, MI, USA).

Cell Contraction Assay

Cell Contraction Assay (CBA-202, Cell Biolabs Inc., San Diego, USA) was performed according to the manufacturer's protocol. Briefly, 397.5 μ l Collagen Solution, 102.5 μ l

of 5xPSB and 14.2 µl neutralization solution were mixed on ice. Human primary aortic cells were detached from culture flasks and suspended in SMC Growth Medium (s. above). 125 µl of cell suspension at a final concentration of 1.2 million cells/ml were mixed with the collagen matrix and 500 µl aliquots were placed in a 24-well plate. The cell-containing matrix polymerized at 37°C and 5% CO₂ for one hour. Then 1 ml SMC Medium was added to the matrices. After 48 hours at 37°C and 5% CO₂, 0,5 ml of SMC Medium was added to each well to reach the following final concentrations: lenvatinib 10 µM, DMSO 0.1%, Bradykinin 10nM (B3259-1MG, Sigma Aldrich, Germany) and BDM 10mM (100x stock included in the kit). Matrices were released using a sterile spatula. Images were taken every 15-30 min for 6 h and then after 24 h. The diameter of each matrix was measured using a ruler and normalized to the vessel. After 24 h, 200 µl Qiazol was added to each matrix and RNA was isolated using miRNeasy Micro Kit (217084, Qiagen, USA).

Study Approval

All procedures were carried out in accordance with the protocols approved by the animal care committee of the Karolinska Institutet (PPE: N119/15 and Amendment N229/15) or the Austrian Ministry of Science (AngII: BMWWF-66.009/0355-WF/V/3b/2016 and amendment 2020-0.547.543) and in compliance with the guidelines on animal welfare of the Committee for Animal Experiments. The pig study was performed in compliance with the EU Directive 2010/62/EU for animal experiments and the German Animal Welfare Act (2018). All pig procedures and animal handling were approved by the Animal Research Ethical Committee of the Government of Upper Bavaria (Munich, Germany; protocol No. ROB-55.2-2532.Vet_02-18-53).

Statistics

Ultrasound data from animals is shown relative to the individual baseline diameter of the aorta (i.e. Figure 1A) and as absolute aortic diameter (Suppl. Figure 1), both as mean \pm 1 standard error of the mean (SEM). Statistical testing of ultrasound diameter measurements of all experimental animal model aortas, except for murine PPE model, was performed using multiple t-test (1 per row) with post hoc Holm-Sidak correction for multiple comparisons (Suppl. Table 1). Due to increased complexity, the ultrasound measurements of murine PPE model aortas were analyzed using a repeated-measures two-way ANOVA approach (Suppl. Table 1). Post hoc pairwise comparisons were thereafter performed using Fisher's LSD test with Sidak's correction for multiple comparisons. qPCR gene expression data is shown, using the $\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}$ -method normalized to housekeeping genes and individual control vessel (fold change= $2^{-\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}}$) as mean and standard deviation. A Welch t-test for unpaired samples of small numbers (parametric) was used with a level of <0.05 considered significant for gene expression data. For comparison of IncuCyte live cell imaging experiments, data is presented as mean \pm 1 SEM. Significance threshold are defined as follows: $*$ = $p<0.05$, $**$ = $p<0.01$, $***$ = $p<0.001$, $****$ = $p<0.0001$. GraphPad Prism was used to prepare graphs. Microsoft PowerPoint was used to establish composite figures.

Author contributions

Conception and design: **AB, VP** and **LM**; Analysis and interpretation: **AB, JP, VP, GW, CO, CK, HHE** and **LM**; Data collection: **AB, JP, VP, SB, GW, EC, JP, SM, HW, MT, AW, CO, JF, JR, JW, JR, CB** and **CK**; Writing the article: **AB** and **LM**; Critical revision of the article: **AB, JP, VP, JR, HHE, CO, CB, LM**; Final approval of the article: **all authors**; Statistical analysis: **AB, VP, GW** and **HW**; Obtained funding: **AB, HHE** and **LM**; Overall responsibility: **AB**

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Figure 1: Effects of lenvatinib treatment *in vivo*

(A) Two-way repeated measures ANOVA analysis revealed significant effects of time, treatment, and the interaction of time and treatment, on aneurysm diameter in the PPE model. Both, systemic oral and local endovascular lenvatinib treatment, starting 7 days after PPE-AAA induction, completely block aortic dilatation (local: red, $n=5$; systemic: dark red, $n=7$) vs. sham-treated PPE-AAA mice (blue, $n=11$) assessed by B-mode ultrasound imaging ($*=p<0.05$; displayed relative growth compared to baseline aortic diameter; corresponding absolute diameters shown in Suppl. Figure 1A; p -value calculations and detailed measurements in Suppl. Table 1; PPE AAA induction at day 0). (B) Double fold change (Fc) plot depicts analysis of RNA profiling (mouse transcriptome array; MTA_1.0). Areas with light-grey background represent genes regulated in opposite directions (rescue effect) upon lenvatinib treatment. *Myh11* displays the most pronounced changes comparing log2 Fc of gene expression in PPE-induced AAA (PPE) vs. control, and PPE-induced AAA + lenvatinib (PPE+Lenva systemic) vs. PPE. The bar chart highlights and indicates direction (up or down) of the most prominent changes in gene expression from the Fc plot (MTA analysis: $n=6$ PPE; $n=7$ PPE+Lenva systemic; $n=5$ untreated 'normal' aorta). (C-E) HE staining reveals a disrupted media with pronounced cellular infiltrates in PPE-AAA (D) compared to control aorta (C). (E) Upon systemic lenvatinib treatment, cellular infiltrates are reduced, with a more compact media and a thickened adventitia, and marked fibrosis. α SMA staining is positive in all three groups, emphasizing a more linear organized media in control aortas and upon lenvatinib treatment. MYH11 is absent in PPE, and highly positive in the media of lenvatinib-treated mice (dark red stain, highlighted with arrows). CD31 positive cells (brown stain) indicate intact endothelial lining in all three groups, but only in PPE few positive cells are present in the media and adventitia (magnification 10x/40x; scale bar 100 μ m).

Figure 2: Lenvatinib rescues smooth muscle cell contractility *in vivo*

(A) Quantification using high power field (HPF) analysis of cell counts for MYH11-positive cells. Systemic and local lenvatinib treatment restores MYH11 positivity in the media of PPE-AAA (****= $p < 0.0001$; one tailed t-test). (B) Ultrasound measurements of aortic diameter are shown for the three treatment groups (PPE: $n=11$, PPE + Lenva local: $n=5$ and sham re-operation (PPE + PBS local): $n=3$) during a time line of four weeks. Relative aortic diameter is calculated in relation to baseline diameter at day 0 (PPE AAA induction) (*= $p < 0.05$; absolute diameters are shown in Suppl. Figure 1A, D; p -value calculations and detailed measurements in Suppl. Table 1; Two-way repeated measures ANOVA analysis). (C) The established AAA (arrow indicates the previous aortic suture from the initial procedure) is prepared from the retroperitoneum, and a local perfusion with lenvatinib is performed (asterisk indicates the perfusion catheter) (D) Immunohistochemical analysis of AAAs treated locally with lenvatinib showing α SMA, MYH11 (highlighted by arrows) and CD31. (magnification 10x/40x; scale bar 100 μ m). (E) KEGG-pathway gene overrepresentation analysis of significantly down-regulated genes (adjusted p -value < 0.05 , $F_c < -2$) at day 7 post PPE-AAA compared to sham (saline) controls, showing baseline transcriptomic characteristics of the model at the timepoint of lenvatinib treatment initiation. Top 15 significantly affected pathways are shown (adjusted p value is given in shades of blue).

Figure 4: Lenvatinib triggers smooth muscle cell contractility *in vitro*
(A) Collagen-based contractility assay to assess AAA patient-derived SMCs contraction in presence of vasoactive hormone bradykinin (grey), contraction inhibitor BDM (black), lenvatinib (red) and control treatment DMSO (blue). **(B)** Gene expression analysis performed on cells embedded in the collagen matrix after 24h showing the lenvatinib treatment effect in comparison to the control exposed cells. (Data are presented in mean \pm SEM; $*=p<0.05$, $***=p<0.001$). **(C)** Western Blot analysis for MYH11 and **(D)** phosphorylated ERK1-2 in control treated (blue) and lenvatinib treated cells (red). Protein bands were quantified and normalized to beta actin and total ERK1-2, respectively. Complete WB images are shown in Suppl. Figures 9A, 10A.

Figure 5: Endovascular lenvatinib treatment *LDLR*^{-/-} minipigs with AAA disease

(A) Transfemoral angiography of the infrarenal aorta (\$=right renal artery to €=aortic trifurcation) on day 7 after AAA induction shows the dilated aortic segment. Radiopaque markers guide the drug-eluting balloon (DEB) (12x20mm) to the lesion. Surgical clips from the aneurysm induction procedure seal the lumbar vessels. The photograph shows the dilated part of the aorta (arrow) at the time of sacrifice (no circulating blood) next to the cava vein (asterisk). *En face* preparation of the complete aorta demonstrates severe atherosclerosis and fatty streaks at the level of the aortic valve, the coronary and supra-aortic branch ostia and at the infrarenal level and the renal artery (#). (B) Singular treatment with a lenvatinib coated balloon (red: Lenva-DEB; n=4) on day 7 after PPE-AAA induction shows a significant aortic diameter reduction compared to non-treated (blue: PPE only; n=7) animals (*= $p < 0.05$; Two-way repeated measures ANOVA analysis). (C) HE indicates a parallel fibrous structure in the non-intervened (normal) *LDLR*^{-/-} pig aorta with marked non-calcified plaque formation. Similar to the murine PPE-AAA model, a substantial MYH11 restoration is detected upon local lenvatinib treatment (Lenva-DEB) compared to PPE-AAAs. (D) Quantification of MYH11 positive cells confirms loss of MYH11 in PPE-AAA minipigs compared to untreated (normal) *LDLR*^{-/-} aorta, and restoration upon Lenva-DEB treatment. (E) Western Blot analysis confirms higher MYH11 protein content in Lenva-DEB treated minipigs compared to DEB-controls (PPE) with progressing AAA. (F) MYH11 Western Blot analysis on primary pig aortic cells treated for 48h with lenvatinib (normalized to beta actin). (*= $p < 0.05$; magnification 5x/20x; scale bar 200 μ m; vessel lumen oriented upwards; complete WB and quantifications are shown in Suppl. Figure 13)

Figure 6: Contractile element MYH11 loss in human AAA and restoration upon DEB-delivered lenvatinib treatment in pigs; proposed mechanism of action

(A) Immunofluorescent staining of SMA, MYH11 and nuclear DAPI in human control aorta and AAA and **(B)** in Yucatan *LDLR*^{-/-} PPE-AAA minipig model untreated and treated with lenvatinib. **(C)** Scheme of the proposed mechanism of action for Lenvatinib in the context on aneurysm development. Lenvatinib inhibits the tyrosine kinase intracellular signal by reducing ERK1-2 phosphorylation in aortic smooth muscle cells. This event is associated to decreased proliferation. In parallel, lenvatinib seems to improve SMC contractility, possibly by MYH11 restoration resulting in a potential slowdown of aneurysmal growth.